

EPR and electronic spectral studies on copper(II) complexes of some N-O donor ligands

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Complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{ligand-H})_2]$ of copper(II) with bidentate nitrogen-oxygen donor ligands, viz. 2-hydroxynaphthaldehydeoxime [hnoH₂], 2-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime [haoH₂], salicyladoxime [salH₂] and 2-hydroxypropiophenoneoxime [hmpH₂] have been prepared. The complexes have square-planar geometry. The effect of axial ligand has also been studied by EPR spectra of the pyridine adduct of these complexes. Spectral features for diadducts are different compared to the monoadducts. All these pyridine adducts have tetragonal geometry.

The complexes of *o*-hydroxyoximes received considerable attention due to structural features, which are of general interest¹⁻⁶. The detailed study of such features and the correct explanation of these unusual properties are independent on precise structural information. The chemistry of these oximes is important in view of their possible application as biochemical models^{7,8} and as semi-conducting materials^{9,10}. In this paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of copper(II) complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{ligand-H})_2]$ of some N-O donor ligands viz., 2-hydroxynaphthaldehydeoxime [hnoH₂] (**1a**), 2-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime [haoH₂], salicyladoxime [salH₂] and 2-hydroxypropiophenoneoxime [hmpH₂] (**1b**).

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

All the complexes are insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, acetone and highly soluble in dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide and tetrahydrofuran. On the basis of elemental analyses the complexes were found to have composition $\text{Cu}(\text{ligand-H})_2$ (Table 1). Molar conductance values of the complexes in DMSO lie in the range of 9–15 $\omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicate that the complexes are non-electrolyte in nature¹¹. The complexes show mag-

Compd.	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Metal% Found (Calcd.)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{hnoH-H})_2]$	Green	275	14.53 (14.58)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{haoH-H})_2]$	Bluish green	270	17.42 (17.46)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{salH-H})_2]$	Blue	280	18.99 (18.93)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{hmpH-H})_2]$	Bluish green	260	16.17 (16.22)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{hnoH-H})_2(\text{Py})_2]$	Green	255	10.63 (10.69)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{haoH-H})_2(\text{Py})_2]$	Green	250	11.90 (11.94)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{salH-H})_2(\text{Py})_2]$	Green	258	12.81 (12.86)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{hmpH-H})_2(\text{Py})_2]$	Green	251	11.50 (11.55)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

netic moment at RT in the range of 1.80–1.83 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron.

IR spectra : In the IR spectra of the ligands, the ν_{OH} stretching vibration is observed at 3450–3475 cm^{-1} as strong absorptions of the oxime or phenolic group. The absence of this band in the spectra of the metal complexes suggests the removal of hydrogen atom and coordination through the oxygen of the phenolic group¹²⁻¹⁴. Another strong ligand

band at 1560–1590 cm⁻¹ assignable to C=N is also shifted to lower frequency (~25 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes, suggesting involvement of C=N group in chelation¹⁵. Weak broad bands in the complexes is observed in the range of 1745–1681 cm⁻¹ assignable to intramolecular hydrogen bridge (O–H---O) bending vibrations¹². Disappearance of the stretching vibration of the OH band, which is present in free ligand is further evidence for (O–H---O) bond formation. It indicates that two ligand molecules co-ordinate to metal ion in a trans fashion. Some new bands also appeared in the IR spectra of the complexes at 460–475 cm⁻¹ and 398–393 cm⁻¹, due to the formation of ν(M–O) and ν(M–N) bonds^{16,17}.

The electronic spectra of copper(II) complexes show four absorption bands at 11050–11120 (ε = 1.5 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), 18620–19250 (ε = 2.2 m³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), 21500–22600 (ε = 4.5 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and 23200–23700 cm⁻¹ (ε = 8.2 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The band observed near 11050 cm⁻¹ is generally not occurred in Cu^{II} complexes having C_{4v} symmetry, hence their assignment is difficult. The next three spin allowed transition are resolved either by Gaussian analysis or single crystal polarization studies and are assigned to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions respectively. The position of bands suggests square-planar geometry of complexes.

EPR spectra of the complexes in polycrystalline state :

EPR spectra of all the complexes in polycrystalline form are of identical nature showing¹⁸ normal features with g_{||} > g_⊥ ≥ 2.02, typical of a copper(II) (d⁹) ion in axial symmetry with the unpaired electron present in the d_{x²-y²} orbital (Table 2).

Solution spectra and frozen solution EPR spectral studies :

The EPR spectra of the complexes under study in CHCl₃ at RT show four equally spaced hyperfine lines characteristic of the copper(II) nuclear hyperfine interaction. Each copper hyperfine lines superimposed to the lines, which are derived from the extra hyperfine interaction with the nitrogen nucleus of the donor ligand atoms. The value of EPR parameters obtained for the complexes are given in Table 3.

Table 2. EPR spectral data for copper(II) complexes and pyridine adducts(polycrystalline)

Compd.	At 300 K			At 77 K		
	g	g _⊥	g _o	g	g _⊥	g _o
[Cu(hnoH-H) ₂]	2.193	2.053	2.099	–	–	–
[Cu(hnoH-H) ₂ (Py) ₂]	2.199	2.056	2.103	2.196	2.051	2.009
[Cu(haoH-H) ₂]	2.202	2.060	2.107	–	–	–
[Cu(haoH-H) ₂ (Py) ₂]	2.218	2.065	2.116	2.118	2.062	2.080
[Cu(salH-H) ₂]	2.201	2.069	2.113	–	–	–
[Cu(salH-H) ₂ (Py) ₂]	2.1185	2.043	2.0681	2.182	2.040	2.087
[Cu(hmpH-H) ₂]	2.198	2.060	2.106	–	–	–
[Cu(hmpH-H) ₂ (Py) ₂]	2.135	2.069	2.091	2.172	2.060	2.097

The values of α and β bonding parameters have been calculated¹⁹ and discussed.

The bonding parameters α, β are useful to measure the covalency of the appropriate bonding. A value of 1 for the square of the parameter indicates a completely ionic character, while a value of 0.5 indicates a purely covalent character. The orbital reduction factors, K_{||} and K_⊥ which are the measure of the spin-orbit coupling constant, λ₀ = 823 cm⁻¹ for free copper(II) ion in these copper(II) complexes are obtained using the expressions²⁰

$$g_{||} = 2.0023 - 8K_{||}^2 \lambda_0 / \Delta E ({}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g});$$

$$g_{\perp} = 2.0023 - 3K_{\perp}^2 \lambda_0 / \Delta E ({}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g)$$

The K_{||} and K_⊥ parameters (Table 4) have been related variously as purely orbital coefficients and are related by K_{||} = ca. αβ₁ and K_⊥ = ca. αβ, where α, β₁ and β are the coefficients of d_{x²-y²}, d_{xy} and d_{xz}, d_{yz} orbitals in the molecular orbitals to which they contribute; thus α measures σ-bonding, β₁ and β are in-plane π-bonding and out-of-plane π-bonding coefficients respectively. By assuming β₁ = 1 (since the ligand has no lone pairs available on the N atom for bonding with d_{xy}), the values of α and β are calculated for copper(II) complexes in this paper. The estimated α-coefficient for all the complexes indicate fairly covalent σ-bonding, whereas β-coefficients suggests very little bonding of d_{xz}, d_{yz} with orbital of axial anions in these complexes.

A comparison of bonding parameters calculated in the

Table 3. EPR spectral parameters for the copper(II) complexes (in chloroform)

Compd.	g	g _⊥	g _o	A (Cu)	A _⊥ (Cu)	A _o (Cu)	A (N)	A _⊥ (N)	A _o (N)
				G	G	G	G	G	G
[Cu(hnoH-H) ₂]	2.190	2.070	2.111	218.9	21.6	86.7	19.5	15.0	116.5
[Cu(haoH-H) ₂]	2.185	2.072	2.109	218.5	21.5	86.5	19.9	14.9	16.9
(Cu(salH-H) ₂)	2.111	2.010	2.103	183.0	41.0	88.3	–	–	–
[Cu(hmpH-H) ₂]	2.183	2.055	2.097	217.3	21.5	87.5	19.2	14.3	16.4

Table 4. Bonding coefficient parameters for the copper(II) complexes

	K_{\parallel}	K_{\perp}	α	β	β_1
[Cu(hnoH-H) ₂]	0.78	0.79	0.78	1.021	1
[Cu(haoH-H) ₂]	0.79	0.82	0.79	1.032	1
[Cu(salH-H) ₂]	0.74	0.80	0.74	1.091	1
[Cu(hmpH-H) ₂]	0.78	0.71	0.78	0.910	1

present study with the parameters for bis(salicylaloximato) copper(II) is useful. The values of α , for the Cu(hnoH-H)₂, Cu(hapH-H)₂ and Cu(hmpH-H)₂ complexes are close to each other but significantly larger than that for Cu(salH-H)₂, suggesting comparatively less covalent character^{20,21} of the former ones. The methyl group or the alkyl group on the oximato carbon is in favour of such a result^{21,22}. However, the β -values suggest very little in-plane π -bonding in Cu(salH-H)₂.

Effect of axial ligand :

Influence of axial ligands on EPR spectra of copper(II) complexes have been studied earlier²³, but the adduct formation is rather weak for these oxygen chelated complexes. The effect of axial ligands in the present work has been explained by using the EPR spectra of the pyridine adducts of these complexes. The adducts were prepared by recrystallising the bis-chelates from their pyridine solution repeatedly. Monoadducts are formed in all the cases except for Cu(salH)₂, where diadduct is formed. The g -tensor values for the bis-chelates and the pyridine adducts are presented in Table 2.

For the monopyridine adducts general features of the spectra remains unchanged but show larger g values as compared to the corresponding bis-chelates. It may be visualised that on addition of one pyridine molecule, the copper atom moves out of the plane. This would decrease the in-plane and thereby also covalency resulting into a positive shift of the g -values.

Spectral features for diadducts are different to that of monoadducts suggesting that the unpaired electron moves on to a molecular orbital, which is a linear combination of the orbitals $X^2 - y^2$ and $3Z^2 - r^2$

Fig. 2

On the basis of above discussion the following structures are suggested for copper(II) complexes.

Fig. 3

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. All the solvents used were distilled before use.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured at RT by Gouy method using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs units) as the calibrating agent. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Hitachi FT-NMR, Model R-600 spectrometer in DMSO-*d*₆. Electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. Microanalyses were performed at the Microanalytical Laboratory, C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Molar conductances were measured on an Elico conductivity bridge (Type CM 82 T) using DMSO as solvent. EPR spectra of the complexes as polycrystalline state and in solution were recorded on a Varian E₄ spectrometer using DPPH as a standard.

General method of preparation. The ligands : A mixture of an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the aldehyde or ketone (0.05 mol) and an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.1 mol) containing an aqueous solution (20 ml) of sodium acetate (0.15 mol), needed to adjust the pH of the solution at 6.5–7.5, was heated on a water bath for 2–4 h with stirring, then cooled. The resulting solid was then washed with ethanol and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. The analytical data of ligands are given below :

Ligands	M.p. °C	Elemental analysis		
		Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	N
hnoH ₂	210	70.38 (70.57)	4.65 (4.84)	7.27 (7.48)
haoH ₂	195	63.54 (63.36)	5.91 (6.00)	9.43 (9.26)
salH ₂	190	61.11 (61.31)	5.34 (5.14)	10.43 (10.21)
hmpH ₂	205	65.12 (65.43)	6.54 (6.71)	8.23 (8.47)

¹H NMR spectra of the ligands in DMSO-*d*₆ give a peak for O–H protons for oxime group in the region of 12.10–12.45 ppm. The singlet for the aromatic phenol (Ar-OH) arises near 12.01 ppm. The signals due to O–H group disappear in D₂O solution. The singlet for azomethine nitrogen (HC=N) is observed near 8.75 ppm. Aromatic protons show multiplet in the range of 6–8 ppm. In case of h₂oH₂ and h₂mpH₂ the signals of methyl and ethyl group are observed near 2.52 and 4.02 ppm.

The complexes : A mixture of a hot ethanolic solution (30 ml) of copper chloride (0.05 mol) and an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the corresponding ligand (0.1 mol) was refluxed on water bath for 3–4 h, then cooled. The resulting solid complexes were washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum dessicator over P₄O₁₀ (yields 75–85%).

The pyridine adducts : The complex (0.005 mol) was treated with pyridine (5 ml) and refluxed on a water bath till it dissolved. On recrystallization the dark green complexes that separated out in each case were washed with ethanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ (yields 70–78%).

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